

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11st October 2022

Accepted: 18th October 2022

Online: 31st October 2022

KEY WORDS

MAUSOLEUM OF SULTAN SADAT

Khaltursunov Erkin Berkinbaevich¹,

Khaitov Narzullo Fayzullo o'g'li².

Candidate of technical sciences (PhD),

Turin polytechnic university in Tashkent¹,

Student 2d level

Turin polytechnic university in Tashkent².

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7266539>

ABSTRACT

Sultan Saodat.complex is an architectural monument in Termiz (10th-17th centuries). This shrine, located in the east of Termiz, was formed in the 7th century. It includes about 20 mausoleums. There are mausoleums of the Sayyid dynasty.

Sultan Saodat.complex is an architectural monument in Termiz (10th-17th centuries). This shrine, located in the east of Termiz, was formed in the 7th century. It includes about 20 mausoleums. There are mausoleums of the Sayyid dynasty. the owner of the surrounding lands, Hasan al-Amir, a descendant of the Prophet (died in the second half of the 9th century) and another source, Amir Sayyid Ali Akbar [1][2][3][4][5][6] mausoleum done Among the people S.Sm. The mausoleums known by the name were built side by side in the 10th century, and the rest, mainly in the 15th-17th centuries, occupying 2 sides of the long courtyard. The mausoleums consist of chorsi rooms (9×9.05 m and 10.15×10.25 m) with a roof and a dome. The mausoleums with domes and domes

on the two wings of the courtyard are on the same plot, and the mausoleum to the south looks smaller due to the number of stairs. The equipment and decorations of the mausoleum in the north-west were made of ordinary bricks (27×27×5 cm) in pairs, and a wavy decoration was created. Embossed brick arches are made in the inner room. The mausoleum in the south-west is a little smaller than the one in the north-west. For these 2 mausoleums, a mihrab is needed on a pedimented platform grid. Ceramic tiles give the building a special charm. In the 15th and 17th centuries, high mausoleums were widely used with star-shaped girish patterns and ganchkori decorations. After independence, the complex was renovated and turned into a shrine.

The leaders of the Sayyids of Termiz - the Naqibs - have been honored with the title "Sultan Sadot" - the Sultan of the Sayyids for centuries. Both terms are used interchangeably, in Arabic "Bab as-sadat madan as-saadat; khubb as-sadat miftakh as-saadat", that is "the door of the Sayyids, the field of happiness; "Love is the key to happiness" is widely used.

According to scientists, the first part of the mausoleum was built during the Samanid period. First of all, two mausoleums were

built on the south-western side of the complex, where ancient graves are located. The intermediate space with a dome connecting these two mausoleums with a high-pitched porch served as a mosque. The mausoleums are luxurious, using baked bricks and decorated with various stylistic designs. Especially during the Timurid era, large-scale construction works were carried out in the Sultan Saodot complex.

In the first grave of the complex lies the hoki of Hasan al-Amir, the founder of the family of Sayyids of Termiz. His lineage,

which is recognized in the Islamic world, goes back to the Holy Prophet (PBUH). It is said that Husayn, the son of Hazrat Ali born

to Bibi Fatima, married the daughter of Yazdigard, the last Sasanian king. Their child was born to Husayn al-Asqar from Ali,

and Ubaidullah from him. It is narrated that Ubaydullah's son Ja'far al-Hujjat was the governor of Medina.

Ja'far al-Hujjat begat Amir Husain, and from him Hasan al-Amir. He came to Samarkand with his relatives in 850 AD. After living there for eleven years, he moved to Balkh. Around 865, he came to Termez and settled there completely. From the time of the Somonites, the Sayyids of Termez were awarded the honorary title of

Khudovandzade. It is in this sense, but in a different form, that the Sayyids of Termez were honored with the titles of "khanzoda" and "mirza" from the second half of the 15th century in the sources of the Timurid period. Besides their names, they were called Musawi, Alavi and many other names and titles.

The potential of the representatives of the family of Sayyids of Termiz has been respected throughout the Islamic world, they have been leaders in the life of society for centuries. Belonging to the Sayyid dynasty required active participation in the socio-political, ideological and scientific processes of their time. In particular, Majididdin Ali ibn Ja'far Musavi, the seventh leader of the Sayyids of Termiz, was one of the leading religious leaders of the Seljuk state in the first half of the 12th century and was known as a patron of scientists and built an observatory in Termiz. The most famous poet born from Termiz, Adib Sabir Termizi, created under

the patronage of Majiduddin Ali ibn Ja'far. In 1212, Muhammad Khorezm Shah gathered his scholars and imams, deprived the Abbasids of the caliphate and declared his vizier, A'la al-Mulk, one of the Sayyids of Termiz, as the caliph. Even after the invasion of the Mongols, the Sayyids did not lose their position and moved the destroyed center of Termiz to the territory of the Sultan Saadat complex. The famous scholar Sayyid Burhoniddin Termizi (1275-1342) who came from the Sayyids of Termiz was the leader of the city until 1231, then he moved to Konya, Asia Minor and became the mentor of Jalaluddin Rumi.

The mausoleum of Sayyid Burkhaniddin Termizi in the Turkish city of Caesarea has been a place of pilgrimage for centuries. Another leader of the family, Khudowanzada Abu-l Makarim A'la al-Mulk

- "Amir al-Shahid" (1292-1344) was the governor of Termiz and actively participated in the struggle for independence against the Mongols. His sons and nephews, according to sources,

play an important role in the life and work of Amir Temur. According to one of the published genealogies, the first consort of Amir Temur was Khanzoda Oliy-Nasab. According to the genealogy of the Sayyids of Termiz, A'la al-Mulk had a niece and a daughter with the same name. It can be concluded that Amir Temur had family relations with Sayyids. This reality is proven throughout history: many Timurids were related to Sayyids through marriages. As a result of intermarriage, the family of Timurids and Sayyids became closely connected. Amir Temur bequeathed to his descendants to cherish Sayyids. The

Timurids were loyal to this testament and buried the representatives of the Sayyids of Termiz in Shahi Zinda in Samarkand, while in Shahrisabz, the Gumbazi Sayyidon mausoleum, built by Ulug'bek in 1437, originally named "Avlodi mubarak" became the tomb of the Sayyids of Termiz. "Sultan Sadot" Abul Maoli died in 1459 and is buried in Gumbazi Sayyidon. Sayyid's tombstone contains the genealogy of the Sayyids of Termiz. Sayyids of Termiz have a certain status during the Shaibani period and later. Shaibani Khan brings a bride from the Sayyids of Termiz to his son Muhammad Temur Sultan.

There is information that Abdullah Khan II visited Sultan Saodot and repaired the mausoleum. In the history of the Islamic world, Tirmidzis are distinguished by their knowledge and talents in science and culture. Among them are representatives of the family of Sayyids: Astronomer Jalaluddin Ja'far ibn Husain at-Tirmizi,

Physician, author of the book "Mujarrabat", i.e. "Tested Medicines", dedicated to the field of description and use of drugs, Muhammad Ma'sum ibn Sayyid al-Hasani at-Tirmizi, " Among them are Mir Muhammad Salih Termizi, who wrote the historical work "Munaqibi Murtazavi", and Khoja Samandar Termizi, the author of

"Dastur al-Mulk". The famous artist Mir Sayyid Ali, who came from the Sayyid family of Termiz, served in Humayun's palace in India. Until the 30s of the 20th century, pilgrims visited the mausoleum of Muhammad Hakim Termizi on Wednesday and the mausoleum of Sultan Saadat on Thursday. However, as a result of the

policy of the Shura system, pilgrimage was prohibited, the gatehouse of the complex was demolished and the bricks of the house were taken away. The tombstones on the graves have been removed. Provide the history of the family of Sayyids of Termiz, the prosperity and development of the country

References:

1. Narshakhi Abu Bakr Muhammad. The History of Bukhara Paperback». Tashkent. December. 1, 2011.
2. Narshakhi Abu Bakr Muhammad. O'zbekiston tarixi. Tashkent, 2004.
3. <https://usefultravelarticles.com/6936-sultan-saadat-mausoleum-ensemble-description-and-photo-uzbekistan-termez.html>